

Collaboration at the phylum level: Co-authorship and acknowledgment patterns in the world of the water bears (phylum Tardigrada)

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Abstract

Two forms of researcher collaboration are examined in the literature associated with the phylum Tardigrada (water bears) between the publishing years 1980-2021 inclusive —co-authored papers and personal acknowledgments. Articles analyzed were retrieved from the Web of Science or from the archives of the *Tardigrade Newsletter*. Research goals include studying structure and trends in co-authorship and personal acknowledgments in a research area not tied to laboratory work and continuing to develop a personal acknowledgments classification scheme for life sciences research. This interim report includes publication trends over 1980-2021, a weighted co-author map for 2009-2017 (4+ co-authored publications per year), and acknowledgment profiles for two prominent researchers in the same time period. Annual publication counts fluctuated but tended to rise over time, with a substantial number of articles reporting new species of tardigrades. In 2009-2017, co-author clusters included a wide range of countries and co-author networks, from single laboratories to a broad international collaboration. While both acknowledgment recipients were thanked for comments on manuscripts in preparation, one also provided help in editing English and the other was a source for reference materials. Categories for reference materials and acknowledgment by naming a new species were added to the classification scheme.

Introduction

Studies of co-authorships, citations, and acknowledgments are three ways that metrics scholars have examined network structure in scholarly literatures. Co-authorships show contemporary connections at the personal, departmental/institutional, and country levels. Citations can connect documents, authors, institutions, and countries. Acknowledgments of funding support link authors and their institutions with funding sources; personal acknowledgments can show both relationships among contemporaries and more general sources of inspiration and support. All of these provide insights into the way that scholarship “works”—how it develops and consolidates over time—and the ways that scholars show their indebtedness to others for a wide range of contributions. In particular, studies of personal acknowledgements in published articles can enhance our understanding of the ways that researchers interact with each other, giving and receiving materials and data, sharing methods, and providing useful suggestions and critiques of others’ work.

There is a substantial body of work dealing with acknowledgments, although the majority has focused primarily or exclusively on acknowledgment of funding sources (see e.g. discussions in Desrochers, Paul-Huis & Pecoskie, 2017; McCain, 2018b; Smirnova & Mayr, 2022). Recent articles studying personal acknowledgments data have dealt with topics in a range of “sizes,” including samples drawn from very large multidisciplinary paper aggregations (social sciences, economics, oceanography & computer science, Smirnova & Mayr, 2022), selected journals (5 top economics journals, Baccini & Petrovich, 2021), and the (relatively) small and focused examinations of model organism literatures (McCain, 2013 zebrafish, 2015 sea anemone, 2018a earthmoss). Many studies use high-level classification schemes to categorize

the personal acknowledgments; McCain (2018b) included a more detailed, multi-level classification scheme that necessarily focused on laboratory research (the venue where the zebrafish and other model organism research was conducted).

This Research in Progress report gives a preliminary view of the latest in this series of studies of personal acknowledgments in the life sciences literature. Earlier studies focused on model organism research as a way to capture a coherent body of literature where it would be more likely that many of the persons receiving personal acknowledgments would also be contributing to that literature. The current project casts a wider net than a study of a single species (more journal titles, more organisms) but still retains a focus by studying research at the level of the single phylum—the highest, most general level of taxonomic classification. The group chosen is the phylum Tardigrada (also known as water bears or moss piglets)—a literature of manageable size in terms of total publications in the past 4 decades. The field also appears to have a strong social and collaborative structure. There have been international triennial tardigrade conferences with published proceedings since 1974 in Italy, the most recent being 2022 in Poland. Since 2012, the international research community has been supported by a two-part website (*Tardigrada.net*), consisting of the *Tardigrada Newsletter* that serves both as a repository of papers published since 2001 and contact details for tardigradologists and the *Tardigrada Register*, a “graphic, morphometric, molecular and zoogeographic data on Tardigrada species in order to facilitate their taxonomic identifications” (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2013; Michalczyk, 2023). For 2023, in honor of the 250th anniversary of the discovery of tardigrades, a series of monthly online presentations has been scheduled; it has a subscribed audience of 126 participants from 25 countries (Schill, personal communication, March, 2023).

Tardigrade research covers a broader range of topics than the earlier model organism studies. There are roughly 1500 species of tardigrades known to date, but new tardigrade species are reported every year, based on a combination of DNA analyses and detailed morphological description, along with reports of known species in new geographic locations and environments (McInnes, Jorgensen & Michalczyk, 2021). While they are perhaps most studied for their various environmental adaptations, being able to survive extreme desiccation, very low temperatures, and high levels of radiation, there is ongoing research on all aspects of their biology (see Miller, 2011 and Schill, 2018). Moving to the phylum level—but keeping to a phylum with a relatively small footprint—expands the view of life sciences research that could be captured by studying acknowledgments. Analysis of personal acknowledgments in this more diverse research environment is also a test of the personal acknowledgments classification scheme for life science research (see appendix in McCain, 2018b). An additional intermediate goal is trying to develop a useful graphic display of the relationship between author(s) and those thanked for their various contributions. Suggestions will be welcome.

Methods

Articles for analysis were retrieved from two sources—Web of Science (1980-2021) and the archives of the *Tardigrada Newsletter* (2001-2021). These two sources required slightly different processing:

- WoS search. The fields TOPIC **or** TITLE **or** AU KW **or** KW+ were searched for terms relating to tardigrades. Search terms included variants of “tardigrade” and “water bear”

and the classes Eutardigrada, Arthrotardigrada, and Heterotardigrada. Post-retrieval screening criteria included elimination of (1) all papers relating to the extinct giant sloths and one species of slow loris (Tardigrada is an obsolete order in the class Mammalia); (2) papers including more than one additional taxon (these tended to be field surveys or higher level taxonomic discussions not focusing on tardigrades themselves); (3) papers that mentioned tardigrades in passing but were really focused on something different.

- Archives search. The initial screening is naturally done by the researchers submitting papers to the archives—no giant sloths. But the other screening criteria were applied.

Data collection:

- All relevant papers were downloaded in full-text. The standard metadata, abstract if available, and acknowledgment text (both funding and personal acknowledgments) were extracted from the articles. The articles were also tagged for taxonomic content if they included an announcement of a new taxon or revision of an existing taxon. Retrieved conference abstracts were retained for publication source and co-author data but not used in the analysis of acknowledgments. McCain's (2018b, see appendix) classification scheme was used to categorize the acknowledgment content items; revisions were made as needed (see Table 1 and discussion).
- To create the co-author maps (e.g. Figure 3), authors' names were regularized to a single representation. Reciprocal pairs of co-authors were extracted by hand from each article and repeating pairs tallied across the time period. The list of co-author pairs, ranked by frequency, was submitted to UCINET6 (a social network analysis program) and NETDRAW (a network visualization package embedded in UCINET6). For this report, a weight (frequency of co-author pairs) of 4 articles co-authored over the time period was used.

This paper has been submitted as a Research in Progress report rather than completed research because of the opportunity to expand the analyses both in time frame and in breadth of literature coverage from the original project. The pandemic and associated constraints allowed expansion of the data beyond the initial collection of Web of Science articles on tardigrades covering the years 1980 – 2017 by adding additional WoS years (2018-2021) and the discovery of the literature archives in the *Tardigrada Newsletter* (2001-2021) revealed that there were additional relevant articles not indexed by WoS that needed to be included. Combined, the data set expanded from 818 articles (WoS 1980-2017) to 1275 (WoS plus Archives, 1980-2021). The analysis of the data – co-authorships and acknowledgments—is still ongoing as articles published in 2022 are being collected for analysis and earlier tables, maps, and graphics are revised.

Examples of results

The tables and figures below include some overall results from the full data set and examples of specific results from the 2009-2017 time period (focusing on co-authors and acknowledgment recipients).

Figure 1 shows the growth of the tardigrade literature after the incorporation of the new *Tardigrade Newsletter* archive documents that were not found in the WoS literature and temporal partitions for final analysis. The final total of 1275 included published conference abstracts. Articles missing from the WoS retrieval included non-indexed issues of covered journals (e.g. *Zootaxa*) and journals not covered at all (e.g. *Transactions of the Kansas*

Academy of Science). There is an uneven upward trend over time; it's not clear what effect publication of articles and abstracts from the triennial Tardigrade Symposium has on the counts. The partitions in Figure 1 that group multiple years of publications will be used to examine changes in the collaboration structure over time; 2009-2017 was chosen to for exemplary analyses in this Research in Progress report.

Figure 1. Growth of the tardigrade literature, 1980-2021. Solid bar=WoS literature, checked bar=articles only found in the Tardigrade Newsletter Archive.

Figure 2. Annual distribution of taxonomic articles, 1980-2021. Patterned bar=articles reporting new taxa or revision of existing taxa.

Figure 2 highlights the role of taxonomic research (identification of new organisms or revision of existing taxa) in the tardigrade literature. They constitute a substantial portion of the annual literature over time, although a smaller portion in the more recent years.

Table 1. Ranked list of acknowledgment classes in 1036 articles in the tardigrade literature, 1980-2021

<i>Acknowledgment class</i>	<i>Article count</i>	<i>Acknowledgment class</i>	<i>Article count</i>
3b Comments on manuscript	561	4d Technical assistance	84
4e Collecting organisms	367	1b Research materials	47
3a Specific information or suggestion	285	1d Unpublished data	34
1g Reference materials	246	4c Organism maintenance	26
5c English editing	222	3d Special thanks	20
3d Special thanks (etymology)	191	1a Experimental organisms	18
1c Equipment & facilities	190	5a Manuscript production	17
4a Specific analyses	154	Other	14
3c Advice & discussion	136	2a Unpublished results or manuscript	4
3e Peer support	131	6a Administrative support	2
5b Graphics & Images	105	1e Unpublished software	1

Table 1 is a ranked list of the coded acknowledgments in the 1036 articles that had at least one personal acknowledgment. Two of the bolded classes are changes made to McCain's 2018b classification scheme: 1g Reference materials and a subcategory of 3d Special Thanks reflecting the naming of a new taxon after an individual. In addition, there were many more instances of category 4e Collecting organisms as authors gave thanks to researchers and others who collected tardigrades in the wild than were observed in earlier studies.

Figure 3. Co-authors clusters 2009-2017. (Weight=4 or more articles co-authored with linked author over the time period.) Clusters are labelled by country of main affiliation.

The remainder of this Research in Progress report focuses on the 2009-2017 subset of the tardigrade literature. Figure 3 shows the networks produced with a co-author weight of 4—four papers co-authored in this time period. We can see networks of varying size, including one with two connected subnetworks. The clusters are labeled by the most frequently reported “home base” for the authors in that cluster (one or two had temporary visiting appointments during the time period) and may be referred to by the central authors. Cluster composition varies from essentially single laboratories (e.g. Goldstein/Boothby—USA and Bertolani/Rebecchi/Guidetti—Italy) to the complex network joining the Kaczmarek/Michalczyk group (Poland plus researchers from the Czech Republic, Romania, the US and the UK) and the Schill/Frohme group (all German researchers at this level).

Table 2. Ranked list of acknowledgment recipients, 2009-2017

Top 19 Acknowledgment Recipients, 2009-2017			
<i>Names</i>	<i>count</i>	<i>Names</i>	<i>count</i>
Anonymous reviewers	146	Meyer, Harry L.	15
McInnes, Sandra J.	66	Greven, Hartmut	12
Nelson, Diane R.	29	Dastych, Hieronymus	10
Bertolani, Roberto	23	Degma, Peter	10
Kaczmarek, Łukasz	22	Guidetti, Roberto	10
Bartels, Paul	21	Claxton, Sandra	9
Kristensen, Reinhardt M.	20	Tumanov, Denis V.	9
Michalczyk, Łukasz	17	Fontoura, Paulo	8
Pilato, Giovanni	17	Roth, Eva	8
Beasley, Clark W.	16		

Table 2 is a ranked list of researchers receiving personal acknowledgments from the co-authored articles over the time period. Several researchers were also honored by having a new species named after them; these data are not included in the table.

Figures 4 and 5 are an attempt to show acknowledgment relationships at a level fine-grained enough to highlight a person’s most frequent role as both acknowledgement recipient and as major participant in tardigrade research. McInnes’s very high level of acknowledgments likely reflects her position as editor of the Tardigrade section of *Zootaxa* where she would be a source of both comments on manuscript submissions and assisting with English language issues. For this reason, the focus here is on the next two authors, Diane R. Nelson (USA) and Roberto Bertolani (Italy). Figure 4 can be read as follows. Dr. Nelson co-authored 21 articles and received acknowledgments from 29, most being for helping with the English editing (21 articles) and/or making comments on the manuscript (14 articles). The two top-ranked sources of acknowledgments were the papers in the Bertolani/Rebecchi/Guidetti (BRG) group and the Kaczmarek/Michalczyk (KM) group. All 14 papers in the BRG group that acknowledge her thank her for editing the English and about 1/3 of these thank her for comments on the manuscript. In contrast, 8 papers in the KM group thank her for comments and less than half for helping with the English. She and her US colleague/co-author Paul J. Bartels have co-authored 5 articles with Kaczmarek in the KM group.

Figure 4. Acknowledgments profile for Dr. Diane R. Nelson and cluster links for her two most frequent contribution categories (2009-2017)

Figure 5. Acknowledgments profile for Dr. Roberto Bertolani and cluster links for his two most frequent contribution categories (2009-2017)

In Figure 5, Bertolani shows a somewhat different pattern of acknowledgements than Nelson in Figure 4. Both were thanked for comments on manuscripts in process but, while Nelson’s contributions (comments and English editing) were recognized by both co-authored and non-coauthored groups, acknowledgment of Bertolani’s helpful comments were confined to papers published by one or more other members of his laboratory. In contrast, his contributions to research published by the Pilato/Lisi group were almost exclusively as a source of reference materials used to identify new or existing species of tardigrades.

Summing up

The Research in Progress reported here has two main interconnected goals. The first is a continued exploration of the various recorded ways in which life sciences researchers interact—collaborating and supporting each other’s work and being formally recognized for that support. The second is the continued development of a research tool to categorize those contributions at a level that is useful in getting a fuller picture of the research process and which kinds of contributions are valued by the publishing researchers. One important takeaway from the research reported here is that the way you bound your data collection can make a difference in what you see (true of all bibliometrics/scientometric research). The earlier studies focused on specific model organism research to bound the literature. These yielded a reasonably comprehensive categorization of contributions made and recognized by researchers in the various research areas—consistent with the earliest classification of acknowledgments built on articles published in the 1988 issue of the journal *Genetics* (McCain, 1991). The tardigrade literature gives us a view of a very different type of life sciences research from that conducted primarily in the laboratory, requiring enhancements to the classification scheme published in McCain (2018b). Much of the tardigrade research literature deals with natural history and new species discovery. There is, however, a growing body of work looking in detail at the biochemistry, physiology, and other aspects of the tardigrade as an extremophile—an organism that can survive in environments where most animals cannot—and there is a move to nominate one or two species of tardigrades as model organisms (e.g. Gabriel et al, 2007). The final paper will explore this shift in research focus over time as reflected in the co-author networks and especially the personal acknowledgments as well as discussion of the more social relationships and roles played by authors as collaborators and as providers of data, materials, and services for which they are acknowledged (Desrochers et al., 2018).

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